

Supplementary Table 2: Guild Membership of Taxa

Guild membership of sampled taxa based on tier, feeding style, and mobility. Invaders marked with a *. Some species of bryozoa also invaded, but are lumped with native bryozoa within growth form categories.

Guild	Lifestyle	Taxa
Vagile benthic active predator	Active predator	<i>Flexicalymene, Isotelus</i>
Low tier attached epifaunal passive suspension feeder	Suspension feeder	<i>Vinlandostrophia, Hebertella, Zygospira, Petrocrania</i> , massive bryozoan, encrusting bryozoan, <i>Modiolopsis, Cornulites, Caritodens, Ambonychia, Cincinnetina, Anomalodonta, Hiscobeccus*</i> , <i>Holtedahlina*</i>
Low tier unattached epifaunal passive suspension feeders	Suspension feeder	<i>Strophomena*</i> , <i>Tetraphalerella*</i> , <i>Eochonetes*</i> , <i>Rafinesquina, Leptaena*</i> , <i>Tentaculites</i>
Vagile epifaunal Grazer/browser	Grazer/browser	<i>Cyclonema, Liospira, Holoepa*</i> , <i>Paupospira</i>
Mid-tier Attached epifaunal suspension feeder	Suspension feeder	Thin ramose bryozoans, thick ramose bryozoans, thin bifoliate bryozoans, <i>Tetradium*</i>
High tier attached epifaunal passive suspension feeder (dense fan)	Suspension feeder	<i>Glyptocrinus, Xenocrinus, Plicodendrocrinus</i>
High tier attached epifaunal passive suspension feeder (open fan)	Suspension feeder	<i>Cincinnatiocrinus, Iocrinus</i>
Stationary epifaunal passive predator	Passive Predator	<i>Grewingkia*</i>
Nektonic active predator	Active predator	<i>Treptoceras</i>

Supplementary Information: Guild composition and membership

Guild membership was assigned using tier, food source, mobility, and habitat utilization based on a literature review (see references). The sampled taxa were assigned to a total of nine guilds (Supplementary Table 4).

The guild containing the most taxa is the low tier attached epifaunal passive suspension feeder guild (Table 2) which is made up of taxa that are attached to the substrate and filter feed 0-6 cm above the substrate. This guild contains the taxa *Vinlandostrophia* (Richards, 1972; Purcell and Stigall, 2021), *Hebertella* (Richards, 1972; Purcell and Stigall, 2021), *Zygospira* (Richards, 1972; Walker, 1972), *Petrocrania* (Richards, 1972), massive bryozoans (Watkins, 1991), encrusting bryozoans (Watkins, 1991), *Holtedahlinia* (Richards, 1972), *Modiolopsis* (Pojeta, 1971), *Cornulites* (Watkins, 1991), *Caritodens* (Pojeta, 1971), *Ambonychia* (Pojeta, 1971), *Cincinnatiina* (Richards, 1972; Purcell and Stigall, 2021), and *Anomalodonta* (Pojeta, 1971).

The next largest guild is the low tier unattached epifaunal passive suspension feeding guild (Table 2) which is made up of taxa that are free-living and filter feed 0-6 cm above the substrate. This guild which contains the taxa *Strophomena* (Richards, 1972; Walker, 1972; Alexander, 1975; Williams and Carlson, 2007; Plotnick et al., 2013; Purcell and Stigall, 2021), *Eochonetes* (Richards, 1972), *Tetraphalerella* (Lamont, 1934; Alexander, 1975; Williams and Carlson, 2007), *Rafinesquina* (Richards, 1972; Alexander, 1975; Williams and Carlson, 2007; Plotnick et al., 2013; Purcell and Stigall, 2021), *Leptaena* (Lamont, 1934; Richards, 1972; Purcell and Stigall, 2021), and *Tentaculites* (Lardeaux, 1969; Larsson, 1979).

The mid-tier attached epifaunal passive suspension feeder guild (Table 2) is made up of taxa that are attached to the substrate and filter feed 6-10 cm above the substrate. This guild contains thin ramose bryozoans, thick ramose bryozoans, thin bifoliate bryozoans (Watkins, 1991) and *Tetradium* (Walker, 1972). The mobile epifaunal grazer/browser guild also contains four taxa and includes *Cyclonema* (Wahlman, 1992), *Holopea* (Frey, 1987), *Liospira* (Frey, 1987), and *Paupospira* (Walker, 1972).

All the crinoids present in the dataset are a part of the high tier attached epifaunal passive suspension feeding guild which is made up of taxa which are attached to the substrate and filter feed 10-25 cm above the substrate. In addition to being epifaunally tiered passive suspension feeders, crinoids finely partition niches through differences in feeding ecology (Meyer, 1973; Ausich, 1980; Baumiller, 2008; Messing et al., 2017; Cole and Wright, 2021; and many others). To incorporate differences in crinoid feeding ecology into the guild analysis, the high tier attached epifaunal passive suspension feeder guild is subdivided using higher taxonomic groups as a proxy for filtration fan guild membership (Kammer, 1985; Kammer and Ausich, 1987; Baumiller, 1993). In this framework, flexibles, disparids, cyathocrines, and some dendrocrines are considered open-fan forms, while other dendrocrines, poteriocrines, and camerates are considered dense-fan forms (Holterhoff, 1997). In this study, the dense fanned guild contains the taxa *Glyptocrinus*, *Xenocrinus*, and *Plicodendrocrinus* and the open fanned guild contains the taxa *Iocrinus* and *Cincinnatiocrinus*.

The vagile benthic active predator guild is made up entirely of trilobites and contains the taxa *Isotelus* (Fortney & Owens, 1999; Brandt et al, 1995) and *Flexicalymene* (Fortney & Owens, 1999).

The nektonic active predator guild contains the cephalopod *Treptoceras* (Frey, 1987).

The final guild is the stationary epifaunal passive predator guild which includes taxa that passively predate on other organisms above the substrate. This guild contains only one taxon, the solitary rugose coral *Grewingkia* (Elias, 1983; Neuman, 2003).

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